

D2.3

Material Science Data Repository

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Abstract	The AddMorePower project will use the repository/database NOMAD, developed by FAIRmat. It is a material science-oriented database, adhering to the FAIR principles that offers both public and private instances. The document explains the choice for this tool and the development that are needed to properly use this tool in the project.
Keywords	Data portal, FAIR, data, NOMAD, DOI

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Executive Summary

The AddMorePower (AMP) project federates many different institutes and research infrastructures around characterization and modelling methods to increase the understanding of semiconductor base material. The studies carried out in the project will benefit from the various complementary techniques available at each partner institute. To foster this cooperation, there is a necessity of a fluid exchange of data between the partners, hence the necessity of having a database with a friendly user interface and an API to efficiently share the data in a FAIR way (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

The initial proposal of WP2 was to use the data portal developed at the ESRF as a basis to develop a similar portal for AddMorePower, with the aim to have a shared database for the partners and a way to expose published datasets to the world. After comparing the advantages and disadvantages of already existing solutions, the AddMorePower consortium decided to use the NOMAD data repository developed by FAIRmat, a widely used repository in the Materials Science community, for data management. By adopting an existing solution like NOMAD, the AddMorePower data will be published in a repository that is already known to and used by the target audience – materials scientists. With this the AddMorePower data are more likely to be discovered and reused by other research groups and we do not create another data silo.

NOMAD is an open repository, following the FAIR principles since its creation, dedicated to materials science. It provides a web graphical user interface (GUI) and an API to enable uploading and publishing data to the world. It includes parsers for a variety of different file formats that will extract relevant information from uploaded files and translate information into a common language to achieve interoperability between all the entries of the database.

The NOMAD environment not only provides an online database but also allows local instances of the database to be installed. Local instances are called Oasis and can be installed on any machine to offers the same basic functionalities as the centralised NOMAD instance. In addition, an Oasis can be customised with plugins that will provide new functionalities, tailored to one's needs.

AddMorePower has decided to install a local Oasis as the internal database for all project partners to share data (processed and non-processed) before making it public. Processed datasets that are of interest to the public will be published in the central NOMAD instance, accessible by everyone in the world. As the data produced in AddMorePower is not always supported by NOMAD natively, plugins will need to be developed to support the different data formats produced in AddMorePower.

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Chapter 1 Data repositories

This chapter explains the process behind the decision to use NOMAD [1] as the data repository of AddMorePower. A brief rationale of the necessity of a data portal for this project is exposed in section 1.1, the different options considered for such a repository are listed in section 1.2 and the final decision is explained in section 1.3.

1.1 Purpose of the data repository

During the AddMorePower project, data will be collected and used to advance X-ray- and electron-probe related characterization techniques as well as modelling and simulation methods for the semiconductor industry.

These data need to be curated and stored so they can be found, verified and reused by the community (the objective of making data FAIR [2]). In order to store the data for the long term (beyond the lifetime of the AddMorePower project), a sustainable data repository needed to be identified to ensure they are findable and reusable by the materials science community.

A data policy has been adopted for the AddMorePower project, based on the PaNOSC Data Policy Framework [3] and the ESRF data policy document [4], to define how to manage and access data within the project. According to the data policy of AddMorePower, the data repository needs to be able to store at least the processed data of the project and, if possible, intermediate results which are of value to the materials science community. Raw data which are not easily exploitable by the community at large will be stored at the sources and made public with a DOI if necessary. A good example of this is the ESRF data repository (<https://data.esrf.fr>) which stores raw data from the experiments at the ESRF and provides a DOI for citing the data (e.g. [10.15151/ESRF-ES-1854292147](https://doi.org/10.15151/ESRF-ES-1854292147), see *Figure 1.1-1* for the example landing page of such DOI).

Session **Restricted access**

In-operando X-ray microscopy to visualize power electronic breakdown in time and space

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High-Power electronics are a key in securing a renewable energy supply and advancing the digitization of our society. The lifetime and performance of state-of-the-art technologies are limited by degradation of the semiconductor device structure and the metallic interconnects. This long term proposal aims to characterize the breakdown mechanisms by a series of static and dynamic X-ray microscopy experiments at beamlines ID01 and ID03, supported by the Horizon Europe project ADDMOREPOWER. In operando X-ray microscopy techniques, such as Dark Field and Full-Field X-ray Microscopy, are applied during electrical stress and thermomechanical fatigue testing, to resolve structural changes in time and space. The results will advance the fundamental understanding of degradation mechanisms and provide important feedback for extending the lifetime and performance of high-power devices. The methodology and software will be developed for a future usage of the ESRF community.

Metadata	
Identifier	
DOI 10.15151/ESRF-ES-1854292147	
Proposal	Beamline
MA-6231	ID03
Public release year	
2027	
Session date	
2024-09-24	
Category	
Applied Material Science	
Publisher	
European Synchrotron Radiation Facility	
License (for files)	
Creative Commons Attribution 4.0	
Related DOIs	
No related DOIs were found.	

Experimental data

Data is under embargo until 2027 but could be released earlier. Currently, it is only accessible to proposal team members.

[Access data for experimental team](#)

Experimental report

No report was found for MA-6231. Proposers and session participants may submit it via the [ESRF User Portal](#).

Reference

Figure 1.1-1: Example of a DOI landing page for ESRF raw data

1.2 Data repositories considered

The data repository of the project has to be (1) adapted to materials science data, (2) used by the materials science community and (3) sustainable. There are already many data repositories available therefore an evaluation of existing data portal options has been made by the ESRF as part of WP2, together with the partners in AddMorePower. The following repositories were considered:

1. ESRF data repository (<https://data.esrf.fr>): The ESRF data repository has the mission of storing raw data from experiments carried out at the ESRF under the ESRF data policy as well as the derived processed data and associated auxiliary data. Data are stored for 10 years (at least) and the sustainability is ensured by the ESRF. The ESRF data repository has been certified CoreTrustSeal compliant below. All data from AddMorePower experiments at the ESRF beamlines will be stored in the ESRF data repository. Despite these advantages, the mission of the ESRF data repository is not adapted to storing (especially large) data produced at other facilities from a variety of experimental techniques which are not performed at the ESRF. In addition, the ESRF data repository is not focussed on materials science and therefore not widely known by the materials science community.

2. NOMAD data repository (<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/>): The NOMAD data repository is a data repository dedicated to storing results from computations of materials. It has recently started to include data from material characterization experiments. It is a public repository which accepts data from everyone (there is no restriction on the facilities). The NOMAD data repository is being actively developed and maintained by the NOMAD team. NOMAD is one of two data repositories recommended by Springer-Nature for storing FAIR data for materials science [6]. It is well known in the community and storing AMP data there would expose it to the wider materials science community. The NOMAD repository is financed by the German government and sustained by a consortium.

3. Self-hosted NOMAD OASIS repositories (<https://nomad-coe.eu/nomad-lab/services-nomad-lab/oasis-nomad-lab>): The NOMAD data repository software can be installed locally to be used as a standalone repository at any site, this installation is called a NOMAD Oasis. It is supported by the NOMAD software for sites that want to manage their own repositories but use the same software as NOMAD-lab. This option for storing FAIR data from the AMP project would require a site which can expose the NOMAD Oasis instance as a publicly accessible service as well as provide access to all AMP partners (manage logins and security) and sustain it beyond the end of the project. A number of partners were interested to install an instance of NOMAD Oasis to manage their own data. It was decided this would be a good solution for sites which do not have a data repository yet for raw data and/or want to test uploading data locally before uploading it to NOMAD.

4. Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>): Zenodo is a well-known data repository hosted at CERN which can store data from any project. Data are assigned a DOI and are guaranteed to be stored forever (at least no date is given for their removal). It is widely used in the scientific community. Zenodo is not dedicated to any community and the data have very limited metadata available for searching. Storing data there would not make it easily searchable and findable by the materials science community. No constraints are placed on what can be uploaded therefore it could be a fallback solution in case needed.

5. Other: other alternatives exist in addition to the above. The review article “Data-Driven Materials Science: Status, Challenges and Perspective” by Himanen et. al. [7] lists 21 data infrastructures for materials science. A number of them are dedicated to data calculated by simulation while others are similar to NOMAD in their mission e.g. Materials Cloud in the USA. None of them currently show a major advantage compared to NOMAD.

1.3 Data repositories for AddMorePower

A working group was formed within WP2 of all partners with experience in data management. It met three times to discuss the choice of a data repository for AMP. Meetings were organised with the NOMAD development team who gave a detailed introduction to NOMAD and provided support to install and upload data to NOMAD. The conclusion of the WP2 team was to make a distinction between RAW and FINAL data as follows:

1. **RAW data** – are the original data produced by the instruments doing the experiments and have not been processed.

2. **FINAL data** – processed data which are reusable and relevant to the material science community.

This distinction led to a two-pronged approach for the management of the data and to the decision of the NOMAD data repository (<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/>) as the best solution for making the results of AddMorePower openly available as FAIR data. Therefore, depending on the type of data, it will be stored in different places as follows:

- **RAW data** – will be stored at the partner sites in existing repositories e.g. the ESRF data repository, or in a NOMAD Oasis local instance. These data are not public by default, however, in some cases, for instance, with the ESRF data portal, raw data will become public after the default embargo period, 3 years, following the data policy of the ESRF. Table 1 recalls the initial solutions for raw data sharing of the different partners, as established in the data management plan document of the project (Deliverable D2.1).

- **FINAL data** – these data will be stored in the NOMAD data repository and be made publicly available.

Organisation	Access to raw data & raw data sharing
IKTS	FORDATIS (https://fordatis.fraunhofer.de) is the Fraunhofer research data repository that enables easy and transparent publication of data, while still complying with the scientific guidelines for high quality reproducible research.
KAI	KAI doesn't have its own public raw data storage. However, after clearance process by top management, sharing relevant and selected raw data on open repositories is planned
IFAT	IFAT doesn't have its own public raw data storage. However, after clearance process by top management, sharing relevant and selected raw data on open repositories is planned
ESRF	ESRF data are published via the ESRF data portal and organised according to the ESRF data policy. Data have a default embargo period of 3 years. The identity is managed by the ESRF Single Sign On (SSO) platform. The implementation of Access Control Lists (ACLs) on the ESRF file systems allows for fine-grained access control to directories and files depending on the user's identity. Access to embargoed data via the on-line catalogue (https://data.esrf.fr) of the ESRF is restricted to registered users only. Open data are accessible to all, meaning no login required.
CNRS	Not supported currently, but CNRS plans to learn from the other AddMorePower partners during the project on how to share raw data.
IPM	Not supported currently, but IPM plans to learn from the other AddMorePower partners during the project on how to share raw data.
KUL	KU Leuven also has an Open Data Policy which KUL will conform while publishing AMP data. (https://www.kuleuven.be/rdm/en/policy)
UL-LEM3	Not supported currently, but data can be requested upon demand at the principal investigator ¹ .

Table 1.3-1: Access to raw data and raw data sharing at AddMorePower partners. Adapted from the data management plan (Deliverable D2.1) of the project.

¹ Editors note: This method is proven not to be a reliable way to access data.

Chapter 2 NOMAD presentation

This chapter presents the NOMAD repository. Some vocabulary, specific to NOMAD, are explained in section 2.1, the FAIR principles and its importance are described in section 2.2, a presentation of the NOMAD environment is detailed in section 2.3, the links between NOMAD and the FAIR principles are highlighted in section 2.4 and the NOMAD Oasis database is presented in section 2.5.

2.1 NOMAD vocabulary

- (central) **NOMAD**: Free and open-source online database specialised in storing and sharing data from material science.
- **Oasis**: Local instance of NOMAD, can be public or private, can be customized by user-designed plugins.
- **Plugin**: Python code that can be integrated to the core code of an Oasis, to add additional features.
- **Upload**: Grouping of files that have been uploaded to NOMAD (central or an Oasis), processed and that can be published.
- **Mainfile**: Any file in an upload that is recognised by at least one of the parsers installed in central NOMAD or in an Oasis.
- **Metadata**: Everything that is extracted from a mainfile.
- **Entry**: Smallest searchable unit of a NOMAD database. An entry is at least composed of one mainfile with its metadata attached.
- **Dataset**: Grouping of entries on which a DOI can be minted. A dataset may also have only one entry in it.

2.2 FAIR principles

Facing the rapidly growing production rate of data and its (re-)use in science, clear guidelines on how to store data have been proposed in 2016 by Wilkinson et al. [2] through the establishment of the FAIR principles. FAIR stands for “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable” or lately seen as “Findable and AI Ready”. The idea underlying these principles is that the data produced should be easily handled by both humans and machines (hence the AI Ready part). At first, they should be “Findable”, so richly described by additional information called metadata and indexed in searchable resources. They should also be “Accessible”, hence easily retrieved by a machine through available, open and free protocols, even if their access can be conditioned by an authentication. The data should also be “Interoperable”, so having a well-defined format that is broadly shared by the community and with good documentation. Finally, it should also be “Reusable”, therefore stating clearly the conditions of its reuse through licences but also having details about its origin or conditions of creation. Fifteen guidelines, grouped under each letter F.A.I.R. are described in more details on the GO Fair website [8].

Such principles about data handling are the key to working efficiently with data produced nowadays. Not only do they help to deal with the data they produce, they also foster collaboration by having a smooth data flow between different stakeholders. The FAIR principles have been followed by WP2 in setting up a common data portal for the different institutes of the project.

2.3 Introduction to NOMAD

NOMAD (for NOVel MAterials Discovery) is a project started in 2014 to create an open database specialised for material science. Initially funded by the Einstein Foundation Berlin, the project benefited from different follow-up fundings within the HORIZON 2020 EU programme and gathered more and more collaborators. It is nowadays developed by FAIRmat [9], the NFDI consortium for condensed matter and the chemical physics of solids.

NOMAD is a free and open-source database for datasets about material science and makes them available for everyone according to the FAIR principles. Currently, it contains more than 16 million entries which represent more than 100 TB of data. Initially specialised on simulation datasets (more than 12 million available entries are made with the VASP code below , [11]), NOMAD is opening towards experimental data with the support of the NeXus standard [12]. NOMAD helps to centralise the material science datasets of the community by including the information from other databases in this field, for instance the Perovskite Database [13] or the Alexandria database [14].

One of the distinctive features of NOMAD is the automatic extraction of the data and metadata from the files when they are uploaded to the database. This extraction is made possible through the use of parsers specialised for different file formats. When publishing a file on NOMAD, the uploaded files will be automatically tested against a list of available parsers to see if one of them knows their format. If a parser recognises one of the formats, it will begin the task of reading and extracting all the relevant information inside the files, from data to metadata, creating the corresponding entry in the database and loading all the information extracted in this entry. All this process is done automatically after a drag-and-drop of the files. NOMAD can recognise a certain amount of standard file formats with their number increasing with time, as the development team adds more file formats to the recognised list.

When a file format is not recognised by NOMAD, the automatic extraction can't be performed and their metadata will not be available to document the entry. In this context, it will not be possible to publish this undocumented entry in the database, to avoid having non-FAIR datasets. However, there is still a possibility to document the unrecognised files by writing a descriptive file, using the NOMAD language. Structured under the YAML format, this descriptive file should contain as much information as possible about the physical data, for instance the metadata within the unrecognised files. Then, this information will be attached to the NOMAD entry when published. Using this mechanism, it is then possible to upload any type of file format on NOMAD.

Extracting relevant information from the files and converting them under the same language allows to set filters, based on the metadata, that will be helpful to search for datasets showing specific characteristics. For instance, a search based on the elemental composition of a material is possible in NOMAD, or a search based on datasets produced by a certain simulation code or method, or using a particular experimental technique.

The documentation of the whole NOMAD environment can be found at this link: <https://nomad-lab.eu/prod/v1/docs/>

2.4 NOMAD and the FAIR principles

NOMAD was created before the establishment of the FAIR principles. Nonetheless, it follows the same guidelines that are today known as the FAIR principles.

For the “Findable” part of the FAIR principles, NOMAD assigns a persistent identifier to all the entries in the database and allows any user that has published datasets to mint them a DOI for publications. Each upload of data is described with metadata, like the list of authors, the date of upload, the upload identifier and any reference provided by the users. The extracted physical data from the uploaded files are described using the metadata also extracted from the uploaded files, documenting the data within an entry in NOMAD. Anyone can browse the central NOMAD database and access the published entries.

For the “Accessible” part, the data are kept for at least 10 years, but the metadata attached to the entries “will always be visible to all users” (according to the terms of service of NOMAD [15]). An embargo period of up to 3 years can be put on entries so that access to the data is only possible for the users in the list of authors of the upload during the embargo period. The raw files of an entry are downloadable via the standard HTTPS protocol, either through the web GUI or via the API. Once an entry becomes public on NOMAD, it cannot be erased from the database.

For the “Interoperable” part, each entry in the database can be translated into a JSON file displaying all the metadata extracted from a file in a structured tree. The metadata are stored using the NOMAD MetalInfo schema [16], which ensures that a similar information contained in different files of different formats, for instance, the atomic composition, will be written the same way in the JSON file of each different entry.

For the “Reusable” part, NOMAD can extract all the relevant information from a file it recognises, both physical data and metadata, so it helps in understanding the context of the experiment or the simulation. All the datasets published in central NOMAD are available under the CC-BY 4.0 license, which allows them to be reused as long as credit is given by citing the data DOI. NOMAD, in addition to its own API, makes use of the OPTIMADE API ([17], [18], [19]) to allow for a more general way to search for materials between the different databases that provide OPTIMADE endpoints (25 different providers and 29 underlying databases when writing). NOMAD also recognises the NeXus format (<https://www.nexusformat.org/>) for HDF5 files coming from the photon and neutron experimental community.

2.5 NOMAD Oasis

The NOMAD environment is not only about the central instance of NOMAD, public and open to the world. The development team also implements the possibility to download an image of NOMAD and install it locally on any machine. Such an instance is called a NOMAD Oasis.

A NOMAD Oasis has the same functionalities as the central NOMAD, thus providing an off-the-shelf tool for data management in the field of material science. An Oasis can be entirely private, with a defined list of people that can access the data, or it can also be completely public. It can communicate with the central NOMAD to download entries from it to display and use them in the Oasis. The possibility to upload entries from an Oasis to the central NOMAD is under consideration and should be implemented in the future.

An important feature of an Oasis is that it gives the users the possibility to enhance the core functionalities of NOMAD with so-called plugins. A plugin is a piece of code that can be added to the image of an Oasis to add new features in the NOMAD environment. For instance, natively, NOMAD recognises a specific list of file formats. An interesting feature of a plugin can be to expand this list by adding new bespoke parsers for new file formats. This is, for instance, a use case in the Oasis of AddMorePower for the simulation code DAMASK [20] that is supported in the AMP Oasis only through the use of a bespoke parser plugged to the Oasis image as there is no core parser dedicated to this simulation code in central NOMAD yet. The GUI can also be customised through writing a plugin. This way, the visualisation can be tailored to the needs of a project (see section 3.2.1).

Documentation about how to install and use an Oasis can be found at this link: <https://nomad-lab.eu/prod/v1/docs/howto/oasis/install.html>

Chapter 3 Using the NOMAD Oasis

This chapter describes how to use NOMAD to either search for data or upload new data to the database. A description on the installation of an Oasis is made in section 3.1, the interface of NOMAD is described in section 3.2 and the current status of the Oasis for AMP is explained in section 3.3.

3.1 Installation of the AMP NOMAD Oasis

The installation of the internal AMP Oasis database is made easy with the use of Docker. The image can be downloaded from the dedicated repository below in the AMP Github. All the subsequent steps are explained in the documentation of the repository. Any new version of the Oasis can be easily installed by pulling the new version of the Docker image. This Oasis can be installed on any kind of machine connected to the Internet: laptop, desktop, server, etc.

The access to the Oasis can be restricted by limiting it to an internal network or by defining a whitelist containing the email addresses of the people that will be accepted to use the Oasis.

3.2 Using NOMAD

In this section, we will describe how to use NOMAD to browse the published datasets, visualize an entry and upload new data. There are two ways to use NOMAD: through the API [22] or through the web GUI. The first approach can be used inside programs, to deal with large numbers of entries in one go, the second approach is more visual and user-friendly, but both allow easy access to data. In the following sections, we will detail the GUI for NOMAD. Both the central instance and Oases share the same GUI and API, so what is shown for an Oasis works for central NOMAD and vice-versa.

3.2.1 Browsing the NOMAD interface

Figure 3.2-1 shows the first page one sees when accessing NOMAD (central or Oasis). This is the 'Explore' page that allows anyone to search for any published dataset in the database. Several sections are present: the Search results block (mid-bottom right) that displays the different datasets filtered by the query; the Filters section (left) that shows all the different filters that can be used to query the database; the Navigation bar (top) to switch between the 'Publish', 'Explore', 'Analyse' and 'About' tabs and to log in; and the Query text search bar (the Navigation bar).

Each entry in the Search results section is briefly described by some metadata: their name, the formula of the material, the entry type, the upload time and the authors, by default but this information can be exchanged or removed at will using the three-rectangle icon on the top right corner of the box. To access an entry in details, one has to click the right-pointing arrow of the entry.

To select specific datasets, query filters have to be defined. A user can do so by using the textual field to type the query or specific keywords but that requires a bit of knowledge on how to structure a query. In a more intuitive fashion, the Filters section can be used to activate different filters like the list of recognised programs or the periodic table, to select specific elements or make a specific elemental composition.

The interface can be customised to visually integrate filter features. This is done by using so-called widgets, which are small boxes that represent the datasets by the metadata extracted. One can add such widget by clicking on the boxes labelled 'TERMS', 'HISTOGRAM', 'SCATTER PLOT', 'PERIODIC TABLE' in *Figure 3.2-1*.

The screenshot shows the NOMAD interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the text 'PUBLISH', 'EXPLORE', 'ANALYZE', and 'ABOUT'. Below this is the 'Entries' section. On the left, there is a 'FILTERS' sidebar with categories like Material, Method, DFT, etc. In the center, there is a search bar with the text 'Type your query or keyword here'. Below the search bar, there are buttons for 'TERMS', 'HISTOGRAM', 'SCATTER PLOT', and 'PERIODIC TABLE'. The search results are displayed in a table with columns: Name, Formula, Entry type, Upload time, and Authors. The results show four entries, all by Guillaume Gaisné.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Formula	Entry type	Upload time	Authors
<input type="checkbox"/>	12grains6x7x8_tensionY.hdf5		DamaskOutput	28/10/2024 15:28:25	Guillaume Gaisné →
<input type="checkbox"/>	6grains6x7x8_single_phase_tensionY.hdf5		DamaskOutput	28/10/2024 15:28:25	Guillaume Gaisné →
<input type="checkbox"/>	Infineon_ref_SXDM_final_output_NX.h5		SXDMData	28/10/2024 15:28:25	Guillaume Gaisné →
<input type="checkbox"/>	4grains2x4x3_compressionY.hdf5		DamaskOutput	28/10/2024 15:28:25	Guillaume Gaisné →

Figure 3.2-1: Shows the default display of NOMAD with the Navigation bar (top), the Filters section (left), the Query text search bar (Navigation) and the Search results box (mid-bottom middle-right)

An example of such customisation can be seen on *Figure 3.2-2*. This visualisation comes from the 'Solar cells' use case available on central NOMAD (Go on 'Explore' tab -> 'Use-Cases' -> 'Solar cells'). This display makes use of the periodic table, scatter plots, histograms and checkboxes to browse only the datasets related to the 'Solar cells' study. Using these widgets, it is then possible to select only the datasets containing at least or only 'C' and 'Cu' (to choose in the periodic table), with a certain band gap (to choose in the histogram), to select the datasets based on their efficiency and voltage (with the scatter plot) or by its hole transport layer (with the corresponding checkboxes).

This customisation can be made on the fly when opening NOMAD or, just like the 'Solar cells' use case on central NOMAD, designed by developing a bespoke plugin (only possible within an Oasis).

PUBLISH ▾ EXPLORE ▾ ANALYZE ▾ ABOUT ▾

Solar Cells ?

LOGIN / REGISTER ⚙ UNITS

FILTERS

- Absorber Material
- Elements / Formula >
- Structure / Symmetry >
- Electronic Properties >
- Solar Cell Properties >
- Electronic Lab Notebook >
- User Defined Quantities >
- Author / Origin / Dataset >
- Visibility / IDs / Schema >
- Optimade >

Search: Type your query or keyword here

Your query will be shown here

TERMS HISTOGRAM SCATTER PLOT PERIODIC TABLE

Elements linear

only compositions that exclusively contain these atoms

H 40.3k
 C 40.2k
 N 40.3k
 O 98
 F 49
 Ne 0

Spiro-MeOTAD 21.7k
 PEDOT:PSS 7.27k
 none 2.63k
 PTAA 2.31k
 NiO-c 1.97k

SHOWING TOP 5 ITEMS

Scatter Plot: Efficiency (%) vs Open circuit voltage (V)

autorange
 Legend: pin, nip, Unknown, Schottky

Band gap histogram: Value (eV)

autorange 1/4

20/43 108 search results

<input type="checkbox"/>	Descriptive formula	Efficiency (%)	Open circuit voltage (V)	Short circuit current density (A / m ²)	Fill factor	References
<input type="checkbox"/>	MAPbBrI ₂	36.2	1.028	1.24	0.768	https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201901980 , https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00941-3 , https://www.perovskitedatabase.com/

Figure 3.2-2: Example of a customisation of the web interface. A subset of widgets is displayed: the periodic table, a checkbox filter list, a scatter plot and a histogram. Each of the widgets is interactive and allow to create a filtered query to target specific datasets. For instance, an elemental composition can be hand-made by clicking the desired elements; each dot in the scatter plot can be selected to access the corresponding dataset or a filtering window can be used to select only a sub-part of the dots.

3.2.2 Browsing an entry of NOMAD

Each public entry in NOMAD can be viewed by clicking right-pointing arrow on the entry line. There, information is displayed within different panels. After clicking the arrow, the user is directed to the ‘Overview’ panel of the entry, an example can be seen in *Figure 3.2-3*.

Figure 3.2-3: Example of the ‘Overview’ panel of an entry in NOMAD. General information about the entry is displayed: the list of authors, the method, the program used, the elemental composition, etc...

In this panel, the entry is broadly presented with key metadata like the name of the program used, the method used to produce the data, the list of authors, the references attached, some comments. Visualisation tools can also be displayed, showing, for instance, the primitive cell of the crystal with the lattice parameters. Graphs can also be displayed, showing electronic properties, like band structure or mechanical properties like Energy vs. Volume (see *Figure 3.3-1*). This ‘Overview’ panel will be populated accordingly to the metadata extracted from the files of the entry.

The ‘Files’ panel of an entry displays the list of files attached to this entry. On this panel, all the uploaded files will be accessible and previewed using basic visualisation tools like plain text reader, JSON parser or H5Web. The different files can also be downloaded from this panel, all of them at once or individual files. An example of this panel is shown in *Figure 3.3-2*.

The ‘Data’ panel displays the metadata extracted from the files. The metadata are displayed in a tree-structure, following the metadata schema associated to the file format. *Figure 3.2-4* shows such a panel for an entry. The tree-structure can be browsed and each section (each column, for instance, ‘Results’ or ‘Material’ in *Figure 3.2-4*) can be converted into a JSON by clicking on the ‘<>’ icon on the top right corner of a section.

Figure 3.2-4: Example of the 'Data' panel of an entry

The 'Logs' panel displays the logs created during the parsing phase. Any error during the parsing will be reported in this panel. An example of this panel is shown in Figure 3.3-3.

3.2.3 Upload data on NOMAD

In the two previous subsections, browsing the published entries was presented and the explanations were mainly focused on the 'Explore' tab. To add new entries in the database, we shall see how to publish them with the according 'Publish' tab. The 'Publish' tab gives access to three different sections: 'Uploads', 'Datasets' and 'Search your data'. The last one filters the database to show only the entries that the logged-in user has already uploaded. The 'Datasets' section allows to manage the datasets created by a user, to see their content, delete them or mint a DOI for referencing them. But these two sections need published data to interact with, and this is made possible through the first section 'Uploads'.

The 'Uploads' section displays the user's list of uploads (see Figure 3.3-4). Each upload is briefly described with some metadata and its status: unpublished, unpublished but visible, published. On this page, a new upload can be made by clicking on the 'Create a new upload' button or through the command line provided. As hands-on examples or templates, NOMAD provides several examples upload structures through the 'Add example uploads' button.

Figure 3.2-5 shows the interface of an empty upload, where the files are to be uploaded to NOMAD. Five parts are shown, and a sixth one is specific to an Oasis. The first part 'Prepare and upload your files' is used to add the desired files to the upload and to visually list them in the drop-down menu. The files that are recognised by NOMAD, so-called mainfiles, will be highlighted with the name of the parser that recognised the files. For an upload to be published, at least one of the uploaded files must be recognised, whether the parsing is successful or not.

The screenshot shows the 'unnamed upload' interface. At the top, there are navigation links: PUBLISH, EXPLORE, ANALYZE, and ABOUT. The user is logged in as Guillaume Gaisné. The main content area is titled 'OVERVIEW' and 'FILES'. The upload is identified as 'unnamed upload' with ID 'JEK75F1jQ4C80MkviHHTFQ'. A progress indicator shows five steps: 1. Prepare and upload your files, 2. Process data, 3. Edit visibility and access, 4. Edit metadata, and 5. Publish. Step 1 is active and contains instructions on uploading files, a large blue 'DROP FILES HERE OR CLICK TO OPEN DIALOG' button, and a 'CREATE FROM SCHEMA' button. Step 2 is empty. Step 3 includes a checkbox for public visibility and an 'EDIT UPLOAD MEMBERS' button. Steps 4 and 5 are empty.

Figure 3.2-5: Interface of an empty upload. The five different sections are listed, waiting to be populated when files will be uploaded and information entered by the authors of the upload.

The second part 'Process data' lists the processing status of the recognised files, if it is 'pending', 'running', a 'success' or a 'failure', the 'pending' and 'running' status being temporary ones, eventually resolving to 'failure' or 'success', depending on the outcome of the processing. This can be seen on *Figure 3.2-6*. This list shows all the different entries that will be added to NOMAD once the upload is published. It is possible to visualise each of these entries by clicking the arrow on the right of a line entry. The errors leading to a failed parsing will be displayed in the 'Logs' panel of the entry.

For instance, the upload related to *Figure 3.2-6*, if published, should add three new entries in the database: one named 'Infineon_ref_SXDM_final_output.archive.json', which is successfully parsed, note this is a generic name, same as the mainfile because the JSON is a recognised format but rather broad (a dedicated parser will create a more informative name based on the extracted information); one unnamed related to the mainfile 'SXDM_uncomplete.archive.json' with a failed parsing; one unnamed related to the 'NeXus_experiment_file.nxs' file which is still being processed. The possibility to publish an upload depends only on the presence of at least one mainfile, not on its successful parsing.

The third part 'Edit visibility and access' concerns the list of members related to this upload and who can see this upload. The author is by default the current user and it is possible to add any other user with an account as a co-author or a reviewer. By ticking the checkbox, the upload, even though unpublished, can become visible by anyone having access to the database.

The fourth part 'Edit metadata' allows to enrich the upload with different information. Comments can be added in a text box, URL references can be included and links to any dataset can be made,

whether it is already existing or has to be created. The created datasets will then be listed in the 'Datasets' section of the 'Publish' tab.

3 entries ☰

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Type	Mainfile	Process status [↑]	
<input type="checkbox"/>	unnamed		SXDM_uncomplete.archive.json	FAILURE	→
<input type="checkbox"/>	unnamed		NeXus_experiment_file.nxs	RUNNING	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Infineon_ref_SXDM_final_output.archi...		...ef_SXDM_final_output.archive.json	SUCCESS	→

Figure 3.2-6: Example of the different possible processing status. The 'running' status is only temporary and should resolve to 'failure' or 'success' depending on the outcome of the processing.

Finally, the fifth part 'Publish' (and the sixth 'Publish to central NOMAD' for an Oasis) gives the possibility to make this upload public, after selecting an embargo period, which can be 0, 3, 6, 12, 24, 36 months. For an Oasis, it works the same but first the upload has to be published on the Oasis with an embargo period and then it can be published on central NOMAD with another embargo period. Note that for now, this mechanism to publish from an Oasis to central NOMAD is not functional yet and has to be implemented by the development team. By default, according to the data policy of AMP, the embargo period for publishing data on the Oasis or on central NOMAD is **0 days**.

There are some limitations concerning the uploads on central NOMAD. Each upload has a size limit of 32GB and, there is a limit of 10 simultaneous unpublished uploads per user. However, these restrictions can be modified when working on an Oasis.

3.3 Status of the AMP Oasis

As mentioned previously, an internal Oasis has been created for the AMP project to support the consortium to share the data produced inside AddMorePower. However, most of the file formats used in the different institutes are not handled natively by NOMAD. Therefore, the next step in WP2 is to develop the different plugins required to be able to parse new file formats, integrate new metadata schemas to describe as extensively as possible the data and customize the interface to the needs of the partners. Also, as the link between the Oasis and central NOMAD is not yet implemented, a pipeline to upload files that are not handled by central NOMAD has to be developed, using the results uploaded to the Oasis, where these file formats will be recognised and handled by the plugins.

For now, preliminary versions of parsers for the DAMASK simulation code and for experimental SXDM processed data have been made and are available on the Github of the project [23]. These parsers are developed collaboratively between ESRF and the different producers of the data inside the AddMorePower project. A new parser for experimental TXRM data is also under development. The first CHADA and MODA files created in the project (deliverable D2.2) have been used as a basis for the communication and the parser development. The new CHADA templates that are developed in the ongoing CEN/CENELEC workshop "Materials characterization – terminology and structured documentation" will be used in the future.

The local AMP Oasis is not yet available but should be opened soon, with the instance to be hosted by Infineon.

Chapter 4 Summary and Conclusion

NOMAD is an open data repository for material science that is actively developed and used to federate the data produced in the field. It is sustained by a large group of data scientists and developers and is funded by national and European funds. Originally designed for simulation data with tools to handle files from the most used simulation codes in the field, it is nowadays expanding towards experimental data with, for instance, support for handling of NeXus format. This tool offers the possibility to share data with the world in a FAIR way by automatically extracting useful information and metadata from the uploaded files. Additionally, it makes the published datasets easily accessible through efficient filters and easily citable via DOIs.

NOMAD also offers the possibility to extend its core capabilities through the use of an Oasis, which is a local instance of NOMAD. Each Oasis is customisable with the use of plugins that can be written by the users to tailor the functionalities of the Oasis to their needs. Unlike central NOMAD which is public, an Oasis can be private, providing an off-the-shelf efficient tool for data management at a facility. Oases can also communicate with the central instance of NOMAD, by downloading entries from the central instance and by pushing entries on an Oasis to central NOMAD, though this functionality is still to be developed. The NOMAD environment provides the means to efficiently store datasets locally and privately and to make these results open to the community if need be.

Due to its many benefits, especially integration in the materials science community and the advanced development stage and sustainability (compared to other data repositories), NOMAD was selected as the AddMorePower database for public data. It will enable sharing data and knowledge between the different partners and to publish results in a community portal. Plugins necessary to handle AMP data are currently developed to be installed on the Oasis and to provide an automatic and user-friendly pipeline when it comes to data sharing and later their publication.

Chapter 5 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
AMP	AddMorePower
API	Application Programming Interface
DAMASK	Düsseldorf Advanced MAterial Simulation Kit
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GUI	Graphical User Interface
NOMAD	NOvel MAterial Discovery
SXDM	Scanning X-ray Diffraction Microscopy
TXRM	Transmission X-Ray Microscopy

Chapter 6 Bibliography

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- [22] <https://nomad-lab.eu/prod/v1/api/v1/extensions/docs>
- [23] <https://github.com/orgs/AddMorePower/repositories>

Chapter 7 Appendix

Metadata

Method name
DFT

Workflow name
equation_of_state, thermodynamics

Program version
1.0.0

Program name
MaterialsProject

Basis set type
plane waves

Jacob's ladder
GGA

XC functional names
GGA_C_PBE, GGA_X_PBE

Comment
Materials Project workflow data

References
<https://materialsproject.org/materials...>
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.4812323>

Authors
Materials Project

Datasets
no datasets

Mainfile
mp-1008394/materials.json

Entry id
[_v5ukJyQKbE49hq1oG5En_62gr-](#)

Material id
[9yWGHw4JJAtjy0WNzhuJhpccrIDF](#)

Upload id
[ogY4LwNkQ_W_AlqPFenHDA](#)

Upload create time
01/12/2021 15:08:10

Last processing time
02/02/2022 15:10:17

Processing version
1.0.2/c98acace

API

Material

Composition

Formula	Cl ₄
Dimensionality	bulk
Elements	Cl
N elements	1 (unary)

Structure

Symmetry

Crystal system	Bravais lattice
orthorhombic	oS
Space group number	Space group symbol
64	Cmce
Point group	Structure name
mmm	unavailable

Lattice parameters

A	B	C
4.389 Å	4.389 Å	8.602 Å
α	β	γ
90 °	90 °	121.884 °
Cell volume		
140.708 Å ³		

[VIEW IN ENCYCLOPEDIA](#)

Mechanical properties

Energy-volume curve

Type	Value (GPa)
mie_gruneisen	192.543
pack_evans_james	21.326
vinet	195.964
taut	21.579
birch_euler	24.13
pourier_tarantola	3.705
birch_lagrange	13.773
murnaghan	20.82

Shear modulus

no data

Entry References

Figure 3.3-1: Example of another 'Overview' panel with more visualisation tools, taken from central NOMAD.

Figure 3.3-2: Example of the 'Files' panel for an entry, here with a preview of one of the JSON files available in the entry.

Figure 3.3-3: Example of the display of the 'Logs' panel of an entry. Here the parsing is completed without errors. Any error would be written in red.

PUBLISH EXPLORE ANALYZE ABOUT

Your uploads ? Welcome [Guillaume Gaisné](#) LOGOUT UNITS

You can either create an upload and upload files through the browser:

[CREATE A NEW UPLOAD](#) or [ADD EXAMPLE UPLOADS](#)

Or, you can create an upload by sending a file-archive via shell command:

```
curl -X POST 'http://localhost/nomad-oasis/api/v1/uploads?token=n5RJRuj6S0mrsms3W1rsEg.1UHxoP8H0bEvfZ37YqIotEaV0xs!' -T <local_file>
```

Visit our documentation on [uploading files](#) or show [supported codes](#).

Your existing uploads ↻ <> ☰

<input type="checkbox"/>	Upload create time ↓	Upload name	Upload id	Status	Entries	Published	
<input type="checkbox"/>	29/10/2024 15:57:21	Schema for SXDM processed data	GhvYGxGaQMSL2BMsi5yauw ☰	Process edit_upload_metadata completed successfully	1	🚫	→
<input type="checkbox"/>	29/10/2024 15:56:38	Processing status illustration	nQzAFgxuSWmeNxLkHVk60A ☰	Process edit_upload_metadata completed successfully	2	🚫	→
<input type="checkbox"/>	29/10/2024 15:40:28	Example data from DAMASK code and SXDM experiment	vEs2vepQRwuswcYvfXIAhw ☰	Process publish_upload completed successfully	4	🌐	→

Figure 3.3-4: The 'Uploads' section displays the list of the user's uploads, whether published or not with basic metadata like the creation time of the upload, its name, the status of the processed files, etc.